

To Introduce the History of Our Country to the World Through the Virtual World on the Basis of the Project of VR Glasses in Developed States

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Abstract:

this article reveals ways to introduce our history to the whole world and develop the country's economy by applying the experience of developed countries in the tourism industry. Issues of analysis and study of the place of the tourism sector in the country's economy were also considered. In the study of the place of historical and cultural heritage in cultural tourism, its types, history of formation and cultural tourism, research were analyzed.

Keywords: Tourism, VR glasses, tourist expenses, economic crisis, consumption and income, excursion, catering facilities.

Preface

In the economy of developed countries, the tourism sector occupies an important place. By developing the tourism sector, it is possible to increase the flow of income to the country's economy. Tourism is the release of hordiq and recreational wellness for guest, professional and work purposes-the temporary cost of people from their permanent place of residence in temporary other states or places.

Today, the tourism sector is one of the most productive. This sector increases its income as a result of increasing population employment. While the reforms carried out in our country do not bypass the tourism sector, it is important to digitize the tourism sector and apply modern technologies. It is possible to take advantage of VR glasses to fully acquaint tourists coming to our republic with the history of our country, taking into account their limited time.

The meaning of the word VR, (English: virtual reality) is also interpreted as virtual reality, virtual reality and artificial reality. VR is a world created using technical means, transmitted to a person through his feelings: vision, hearing, touch, etc. Virtual reality mimics both the effect and the reaction. For a robust set of reality experiences, a computer synthesis of virtual reality and real-time reactions takes place.

(Literature review)

R. from foreign scientists in the scientific and methodological issues of the effective development of the tourism industry. D. Colle, In Jans Servaes (Ed), A. Singhal, T.D was studied by Kukhovkova and many other scientists. In the study of these problems I.S. Tukhliyev, R. Hayitboyev, B.S. Safarov, G.R. Tursunova. Sh. Saifuddinov, Sh. Islamov, Q.J. Mirzayev, In the scientific work by Pardayev, many current issues are reflected, such as the effective organization, management, development of the tourism industry.

Research methodology

Analysis and proposals have been formed as a result of analyzing the indicators of the effective development of the tourism sector through economic and mathematical methods in the implementation of the study. In addition, the method of analysis and synthesis was also used effectively in the implementation of scientific research.

Analysis and Results (Analysis and results)

Before the era of computer technology, virtuality was understood as an object or state that did not exist in reality, but could occur under certain conditions.

In the late 1960s, the concept of artificial reality was first introduced by Myron Kryuger. In his 1964 book “the sum of technologies”, Stanisław Lem describes the tasks and essence of the answer to the question “how to create a reality that does not differ in any way for intelligent beings living in it” under the term Phantomology. Far from ordinary reality, but subject to other laws? The first virtual reality system, Morton Heilig (English: Morton Heilig) in 1962, introduced the first prototype of a multi-sensor simulator, called “Sensorama” (Sensorama). Sensorama plunged viewers into virtual reality through short films, which are accompanied by smells, wind and capital noise in audio recording. In 1967, Ivan Sutherland described and designed the first computer-generated canvas. Sutherland's glasses allowed the images to be changed according to head movements (visual thought).

In the 1970s, computer graphics completely replaced the video images previously used in simulations. The graphics were very primitive, but the important thing is that the simulators worked in real time. The first realisation of Virtual reality is “Aspen cinematography”, created at the Massachusetts Institute of technology in 1977.

This computer program simulated a walk through the city of Aspen in Koldo, establishing various ways to show the area. Summer and winter options were for real photos.

The beginning of the use of virtual reality in the 80s appeared in the aerospace sector. Sutherland also had the opportunity to artificially wear large helmets so that pilots could perform flight experiments, thanks to research from NASA and the Air Force. World Lanier called such an experiment a “virtual haicut”.

With the beginning of the 2000s, the main obsession in VR began to decline. However, virtual reality experienced a renaissance in the 2010s. Since Palmer Luckey's game-changing Oculus Rift headset was announced in 2012, companies ranging from companies that start trends to tech giants like Facebook and Google have begun releasing virtual Reality platforms. We are not mistaken to say that players, creators, designers and other stakeholders have stimulated the intellectual and commercial growth of this industry.

To date, virtual reality is being involved in all areas in a wide range of areas. Basically, various additional gadgets are being created in order to enhance the effect of virtual reality. One of these is VR glasses.

What is the function of VR glasses and in what way does it work?

VR glasses partially removed the wall between the virtual world and real life can be viewed as a bridge. In it, a simple image is given that gives a feeling that a person is in sight, and through it offers the opportunity to fully enjoy the image.

During the current period of rapid development, the space and spheres surrounding humanity are developing in this way. Alternatively, the tourism sector is no exception. The rich history of our country, the abundance of historical and notable settlements will definitely not go unnoticed by representatives of other states. Today, in our country, yeti has more than a thousand monuments, including 2,500 architectural monuments. Today, the very kata part of them remains unnoticed. Mainly tourists are limited to visiting famous and few historical sites. The main reason for this is the length of time spent on the road and the incompleteness of the information provided by the guides. On this basis, tourists who visit are limited to a narrow circle of memories about our country.

On the basis of the project, it is envisaged to enrich the tourism sector with the help of the latest technologists. In the implementation of the project, it was noted to what extent it was fruitful and, in addition, its scarcity. First of all, we will see on the scale of the city of Samarkand, because of the abundance of historical objects in Samarkand and the distance between them, tourists who visit for a short period of time will not be able to enjoy a sufficient historical environment.

In solving this problem, the project "Virtual tour" will be launched. The main goal of the project is to make tourists look at the rich history of our country, based on the delivery of more information in the short term and the correct implementation of, Time management. In the implementation of the project, a room with a capacity of 15 people will be built near any historical site. The cabin will be equipped with modern VR technologies designed for 15 people inside. The cabin will be dark inside and equipped with a small number of lighting fixtures. The reason will be to attract virtuality as part of more VR technologies. Designed for the number of people brought in, VR comes with goggles, earbuds, virtual motion jostets, and comfortable seats. In addition to it, General Software will be created. A virtual praxect of steps, historical places and objects will be created, which will receive a lot of attention in our country. In the project, users are provided with full-fledged freedom of movement and observation, based on virtual reality. They can take their time off based on their situation and plan their next plans while saving their valuable time.

The project works on the principle of self-sufficiency. That is, the spent electro energy, service services, etc. will go during the voluntary time payment system. In this case, without any limits, users are charged with respect to the time, calculating their time, based on the timer set after entering and settling. In this, the participation of Human Services and the human factor is also reduced, and with a small investment requirement based on the principle of the campyuterized system, it is compensated by an effective income.

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